

Proposed Marketing Strategy to Increase Parents' Enrollment for Inclusive School (Case Study: Alfa Centauri Primary School)

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ABSTRACT: Education is essential for all human beings with noble goals individually, namely to increase the standard and quality of life, and collectively, to contribute socially to a more prosperous society. An important role is held by formal educational institutions with a set of facilities that they have for the quality of educational services provided to all their students. Elementary schools which are the first and main level of education need to ensure that the quality of services they provide from all aspects can contribute significantly to all students. The concept of inclusiveness which is a friendly service concept for all people is a trend and a special attraction in the world of education today. Educational institutions (including inclusive primary schools) that require financial stability require good business execution to survive facing competition in the market. Alfa Centauri Primary School, which is one of the players in the industry, feels the intense competition within it. For the last six years, Alfa Centauri Primary School has not been able to meet the quota of students they receive, so it can be said that their performance is still not optimal. It is necessary to improve, evaluate and form a good marketing strategy to be able to get consumers, where the actual consumers are parents of students. This study uses qualitative and quantitative approaches in data collection and processing. The analysis boils down to two perspectives, internal analysis using marketing mix analysis, STP, and VRIO; as well as external analysis using competitor analysis, Porter's Five Forces, PESTLE, and customer analysis. There are findings in the customer analysis that the school environment and school accessibility are two things that influence parents' enrollment intentions in sending their children to inclusive private elementary schools. Optimizing social media, strategic collaboration, providing shuttle services, optimizing personalization-based learning, creating a comfortable learning environment, and utilizing activities outside the classroom are marketing strategies formulated in this study to increase the number of registrants from Alfa Centauri Primary School.

KEYWORDS: Enrollment Intention, Inclusive School, Marketing Strategy, Parents' Enrollment.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a basic need for all human beings, in which education offers learning and the formation of mindsets for all students. Education has three functions, including qualification (becoming a qualifying individual in a field), socialization (becoming a person who can fit in social life), and subjectification (becoming a subject; which can have an impact and effect on conditions), in which each function will shape the quality of individuals who also play a role in education for a better life [1]. Primary/elementary school in this case plays an important role as the first and foremost place of formal education for each individual. In the education industry (including in Indonesia), "players" in the industry are not fully controlled and monopolized by the government, but the private sector also contributes to the creation of results from education. The Indonesian government "controls" the primary school industry through public primary schools of 88.69% of the total 148,673 primary schools, which means that only 11.3% are owned by the private sector [2]. Even though schools offer noble values and missions for each individual, education and schools (including primary schools) that are managed by the private sector are business entities that require profit for the company's sustainability. One of the revenue streams that is relied upon and prioritized by private schools is the tuition fee paid by students. Like any business entity in general, having healthy finances is very necessary. In this case, marketing efforts from schools (especially private schools) are needed to be able to capture customers according to the targets and capabilities of the school itself. Inclusive schools are a new trend and an alternative choice for parents in sending their children to school. Previous research shows that parents of students have positive attitudes towards inclusive education which illustrates the reasons parents of non-special needs students also choose inclusive schools for their children [3]. This research will discuss the marketing aspects of Alfa Centauri Primary School to realize its best business performance.

BUSINESS ISSUE

As a private school that depends on its main income, namely the payment of school fees from its students, Alfa Centauri Primary School is also in business and competes with other elementary schools for income. As can be seen from the data in the **Figure 1**, Alfa Centauri Primary School has not been able to meet the maximum quota for admitting new students in the last 6 years.

Figure 1. Alfa Centauri Primary School student admission data

The quota determined by Alfa Centauri Primary School is 20 students per class, this is due to provisions from the Dinas Pendidikan Kota Bandung which requires one class to contain between 20-28 students for the elementary level [4]. If one class is occupied by less than 20 students, the certified teacher's salary cannot be paid. The quota has not been fulfilled in the last few years and the increasing target in the coming academic year has made an increase in new student admissions something that Alfa Centauri Primary School needs to achieve. Yayasan Taqwa Cerdas Kreatif as a foundation also oversees Alfa Centauri Junior High School and Alfa Centauri Senior High School, where the performance of these two entities can be said to be good. For the last 10 years, junior and senior high school students have always had sufficient quotas as well as rejected many registrants, and the number of registrants is always increasing from year to year. The success of Alfa Centauri Middle and High Schools has not been well followed by Alfa Centauri Primary School. One of the “ingredients” or aspects of junior and senior high school marketing is selling the "success" of alumni entering favorite top high schools or universities. This characteristic is not shared by elementary schools in general, so other value propositions are needed that can be used as a reference in the application of marketing efforts. The challenge faced by Alfa Centauri Primary School is to get a lot of registrants for elementary school students during intense competition. There needs to be a marketing plan that adapts to existing conditions and the value proposition of Alfa Centauri Primary School in the hope of increasing student enrollments from time to time.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

This research focuses on Alfa Centauri Primary School which is categorized as an inclusive private school. Inclusive schools are schools that strive to realize universal rights by seeking friendly learning activities for all children, including children with disabilities and special needs [5]. The parties that play the most role in the selection of primary schools for children are their respective parents. Parents do not only act as parties who consider where their children go to school, parents can also be said to be customers of the primary school itself. So that the theoretical foundation or reference used is related to the factors that influence parents in sending their children to private primary school. Private school itself is specifically linear with this research because considering that most regions in Indonesia have used the zoning policy system to enter public primary school.

A. School Curriculum and Syllabus

School curriculum and syllabus are essential things related to the learning that will be conveyed or taught to students. The freedom of private schools that are not fully bound by government regulations regarding education, allows private schools to incorporate additional values that are in accordance with the market and the development of the times, one of which is religious values. In choosing a private school, the majority of parents choose a private school that has a religious value base [6]. Apart from religious values, parents' considerations in choosing a school for their children include morals, values, family and character development [7].

B. School Environment and Facilities

Schools need physical buildings, facilities, and an environment that acts as a support for learning activities and the delivery of values by school management to customers (students and their parents). Adequate facilities also help students concentrate and understand lessons well. The educational environment is a serious consideration by parents of students because of the convenience of their children in socializing and learning. The reason for the majority of students' parents choosing private schools over public schools was because the environment and school facilities were not good and the classes were overcrowded [8]. An environment that "forces" to be productive is also another consideration for parents in choosing a school [9].

C. School Performance

School performance is also one of the considerations for the good or bad of the school, because this aspect is one of the measurements of the future outcomes of individuals and society as a whole. A "healthy" and supportive school environment is the main key in supporting academic performance and achievement of a school [9]. School consistency in maintaining academic quality and performance is also one of the things parents consider in choosing a school for their child [7].

D. School Location

Aspects of school location in terms of the location of the school and its relation to the surrounding environment. It can be said that the location of a school is strategic if there is a balance of supply and demand for the school. Parents consider the accessibility and convenience of the location occupied by the school [6]. Convenience can also be interpreted as the availability or absence of transportation provided by the school [10].

E. Teacher's Quality

The performance of services offered by schools is inseparable from the capacity and capability of the teachers who teach at the school. Teacher quality which includes the dedication that the teacher gives, academic-based teaching, and being able to guarantee student safety is an important feature that is considered by parents [7]. The features above can be narrowed down into three aspects including the knowledge that teachers have, interpersonal skills, and technical skills [6].

F. Parent's Intention to Enroll Their Child(ren)

Normally, parents want the best for their children, including basic education. It is the responsibility of parents to provide comfort, safety, and support for children in getting the best education so that they can become quality individuals in the future. In terms of age maturity, children at elementary school age do not yet have maturity in assessing and choosing which school or education is right for them, so this is an important basis for why customers from private schools are more appropriately assigned to students' parents. They are also the party that pays for the services offered by the school. Several previous studies have examined parental involvement in choosing their child's school [6]–[10]. This research will specifically examine parents' intention to enroll their children with the object of inclusive private elementary schools.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This research model adopts research that has been conducted by previous study [6]. The selection of this research model was based on the similarity in the scope of research by previous study that previously had private school research objects. Previous research [6] conducted research on the factors that influence parents' decisions in choosing private schools for their children. The variables used in this study also adopted the variables in the research model. There is a modification to the dependent variable, namely being a parent's intention to enroll their child(ren), which in this study is more specific to inclusive private schools. The research model is illustrated in the **Figure 2**:

Figure 2. Research framework

The variables in the model will produce hypotheses that will be tested in this study. The following are the hypotheses in this study (see

Table 1):

Table 1 Research hypotheses

Hypotheses	Descriptions
H ₁	School curriculum and syllabus have a positive effect on parents' intention to enroll their child(ren) to public inclusive school
H ₂	School environment and facilities have a positive effect on parents' intention to enroll their child(ren) to public inclusive school
H ₃	School performance has a positive effect on parents' intention to enroll their child(ren) to public inclusive school
H ₄	School location has a positive effect on parents' intention to enroll their child(ren) to public inclusive school
H ₅	Teachers' quality has a positive effect on parents' intention to enroll their child(ren) to public inclusive school

The variables in this study are latent variables, meaning variables that cannot be measured directly, so indicators are used to measure variables [11]. The following is the operational definition of the variables described in the **Table 2**:

Table 2 Indicator variable definition

Latent Variable	Indicator Variable	Indicator Variable Definition
School Curriculum and Syllabus	CS1	Respondents feel that moral education is important for their children [6]
	CS2	Respondents feel religious/religious values are important for their children [6]
	CS3	Respondents feel character development is important for their children [6]
School Environment and Facilities	EF1	Respondents feel that the physical school building is important for their children [6]
	EF2	Respondents feel school facilities are important for their children [6]
	EF3	Respondents feel the quality of school management is important for their children [6]
	EF4	Respondents feel that a social perspective on school is important for their children [6]
	EF5	Respondents feel the number of students per class is important for their children [6]
School Performance	SP1	Respondents feel that the academic achievement of the school is important for their children [6]
	SP2	Respondents feel that a healthy teaching and learning environment is important for their children [6]
	SP3	Respondents feel that the cleanliness of the school environment is important for their children [6]
School Location	L1	Respondents feel that the convenience of the school environment (based on location) is important for their children [6]
	L2	Respondents feel that a strategic school location is important for their children [6]
	L3	Respondents feel that the proximity of schools is important for their children [6]
Teachers' Quality	TQ1	Respondents felt the teacher's level of knowledge was important for their children [6]
	TQ2	Respondents feel that the interpersonal skills possessed by teachers are important for their children [6]
	TQ3	Respondents feel that the technical skills possessed by teachers are important for their children [6]
Parent's intention to enroll their child(ren)	I1	Respondents have the intention to send their sons/daughters to Inclusion Private Elementary Schools [12]
	I2	Respondents plan to send their sons/daughters to Inclusion Private Elementary Schools [12]
	I3	Respondents hope that their sons/daughters will go to Inclusion Private Elementary School [13]
	I4	Respondents are determined to send their sons/daughters to Inclusion Private Elementary Schools [12]
	I5	The respondent will send your son/daughter to Inclusion Private Elementary School [13]

METHODOLOGY

The following is a research design framework that contains a sequence of steps in carrying out this research. Through this framework, it is hoped that it can assist researchers in identifying and solving problems in an orderly and systematic manner. The research design used in this study can be seen in the **Error! Reference source not found.:**

Figure 3. Research design

This research used two analyses after data collection, internal analysis and external analysis. The internal analysis of an organization is a critical component in understanding its strengths and weaknesses owned by the company. The tools used in this internal analysis include marketing mix, STP, and VRIO. The external analysis of an organization is also a fundamental process for assessing the opportunities and threats presents in the broader operating environment. The tools used in this internal analysis include competitor analysis, Porter’s five forces, PESTLE analysis, and customer analysis. The next analysis is SWOT analysis which is an acronym for Strengths-Weaknesses-Opportunities-Threat where each element is taken from internal and external analyzes that have been done before. Internal analysis will enter into the elements of strengths and weaknesses, while external analysis will enter into elements of opportunities and threats. The goal of SWOT analysis is to match the strengths of the company with existing opportunities while eliminating or overcoming weaknesses and minimizing threats [14]. The strategies that have been formulated from the TOWS matrix are selected according to the feasibility and ability of the company then the strategies will be processed in QSPM.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section presents results from collected data and detailed analysis of the data itself. This chapter outlines the analysis, business solution, and implementation plan.

A. Internal Analysis

The data that has been obtained from interviews and observations is used as the basis for several internal analyzes below, including the marketing mix, STP, and VRIO.

1) Marketing Mix

Because Alfa Centauri Primary School is a service company, in preparing this marketing mix, an analysis is first carried out which helps identify aspects of People, Process, and Physical Evidence using the Service Blueprint.

- Product
Education at the elementary level refers to several main values, namely faith (Islam), technological prowess, inclusiveness, and character education.
- Price
The pricing strategy used by Alfa Centauri Primary School uses cost-based pricing and market-oriented pricing in comparison to prices applied by competitors.
- Place
Physical building at Jl. Terate No. 10, Samoja, Kec. Batununggal, Kota Bandung (offline); educational facilities such as online meeting platforms, e-library, online presence, and collaborative learning tools (online); and hybrid class
- Promotion
Offline promotion such as open house, promotion activities to several kindergartens, brochures, banners, and school fair; online promotion such as website and social media marketing.
- People
Organizational structure that consists of management, teachers, learning supporting unit, staff, IT Team, financial team, extracurricular teacher, administration, counselors
- Process
Visit the website, do online registration. Visit the school, test registration, doing selection test, accepted as student, pay registration fee. Visit the school using school uniform, enter classroom, student participates in learning activities. Student participates in extracurricular activities. Students are active in school facilities. Parents or guardians drop-off/pick-up students. Student do exam test. Students receive exam results. Parents request information from school. Parents receive their children's student report. Parents or students do a counseling of a problem. Students use the computer facilities that support education process. Doing learning activities (especially for students with special needs)
- Physical Evidence
Website, physical building: school, physical building: class, letter of evidence, bank account number, school uniform, educational materials, extracurricular program, physical building: supporting facilities, physical building: drop-off/pick-up area, exam sheets, exam results, physical building: receptionist office, student report, physical building: school counselors, physical building: computer lab, physical building: learning support unit room.

2) STP

- Segmenting
In the first part, namely segmenting, the researcher divides into three groups based on two categories, namely psychography and geography. All segment groups are determined based on the Measurable-Accessible-Substantial-Differentiable-Actionable rule (see table).

Table 3. Customer segmentation

Category	Segment A	Segment B	Segment C
Psychographic			
Attitudes	Parents or guardians who view education as a priority and are	Parents or guardians who view education as a secondary or tertiary	Parents or guardians who view education as the least priority

	willing to make sacrifices to ensure their child's success	priority, so they won't spend a lot of money for education	
Beliefs	Parents or guardians who believe that a high-quality education is key to their child's future success and are willing to invest in it	Parents or guardians who believe that education play an important role for children success, but mediocre is enough	Parents or guardians who believe that education is not a most important role for children success, so the most important thing for children is to work to help parents
Values	Parents or guardians who value academic excellence and want their child to attend a school with a rigorous curriculum	Parents or guardians who think their children need to go to school but wherever "the important thing is to go to school"	Parents or guardians who not value academic/education as an important thing of life
Lifestyle	Parents or guardians who lead busy and active lives but still prioritize their child's education and religiosity	Parents or guardians who want to have more time spend with their children at home (so they tend to choose home-schooling)	Parents or guardians that have cautious behavior and prefer to stick with tried-and-true service rather than luxury or trendy one
Geographic			
Location	Families who live in or near affluent neighborhoods, where there is a high demand for quality education (wealthy well educated family housing area)	Families who live in or near unaffluent neighborhoods, where there is no high demand for quality education	Families who live in student housing areas, commercial area, or industry area
Proximity to school	Bandung City, radius 7 km from school	Bandung City, radius >7 km from school	Bandung District (outside Bandung City)

- Targeting
Based on the segmentation above, Alfa Centauri Elementary School targeted **Segment A**
- Positioning
For high-class parents that have a child in elementary school age (5-12) that want a good education with character development and Islamic value, Alfa Centauri Elementary school offers a curriculum that is derivative from tutoring Sony Sugema College (SSC) which means quality trusted. Alfa Centauri Elementary School also claims themselves an inclusive school under psychologist supervision, which assures that every student will feel safe and get a good education.

3) *VRIO*

Table 4. VRIO analysis

Attributes				O	Impact
Tangible Resources					
Physical building and infrastructure					Competitive parity
Technological resources					Temporary competitive parity
Curriculum & teaching materials					Temporary competitive advantage
Financial resources					Competitive parity
Learning Support Unit (for students with special needs)					Temporary competitive advantage

Intangible Resources					
Experienced & qualified teachers					Competitive parity
Reputation & brand image					Sustained competitive advantage
Strategic partnership					Unused competitive advantage
Parental and alumni engagement					Competitive parity

B. External Analysis

1) *Competitor Analysis*

Table 5. Competitors analysis

Category	Alfa Centauri	Mutiara Bunda	Taruna Bakti	Al Azhar
School value	Faith (Islam), technological prowess, inclusiveness, and character education.	Building Bright Futures, and Islamic Creed	Honesty, Tolerance, Resilience, Discipline, Creativity, Independence	Creative, Active, Religious, Independent, and Good Manner
Price	Registration: Rp250.000 Psychological test: Rp550.000 Educational donation: Rp26.500.000 Educational development contribution: Rp1.250.000 Activity fee/year: To be announced Assistance fee/month: Rp2.250.000 Total: >Rp30.800.000	Registration: Rp1.300.000 Development: Rp35.000.000 Activities fee/semester: Rp3.500.000 Monthly dues: Rp2.350.000 Total: 42.150.000	Registration: Rp550.000 Development (dana pengembangan sekolah): Rp11.000.000 Development (dana pembangunan sekolah): Rp11.000.000 Monthly dues: Rp1.500.000 Educational development fund: To be announced Total: >Rp24.050.000	Registration: Rp350.000 Entry tuition fee: Rp27.000.000 Fee for foundation: Rp200.000 Educational fund: Rp1.225.000 Total: Rp28.775.000
Inclusiveness	Yes	Yes	No	No
Foundation Coverage	Bandung	Bandung	Bandung	National
Strategic Location	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Phone Apps	No	No	No	Yes
Instagram Followers	1945	2550	1707	4436
Instagram Content Type	Poster-type Student achievement (gif) Article tips (photo) Event documentation (video)	Article tips (photo) Event documentation (video)	Event documentation (video) Student achievement (photo) Article tips (photo)	Article tips (photo) Event documentation (video) Student achievement (photo) Human-centric content
Instagram Content Strengths	Complete information	Child-design type High-quality photo and video	Tidy story highlights Good reels production	High-quality photo and video Variety content Complete information

2) Porter's Five Forces

- Competition in the industry

The industry (in Bandung City) faces high competition with a total of 483 elementary schools, including 209 private schools [15]. This indicates a highly competitive environment where schools need to differentiate themselves to attract students and maintain a competitive edge. Schools may need to focus on their unique offerings, such as inclusive education practices or specialized programs, to stand out in the market.

- Potential of new entrants into the industry

The barriers to entry for new schools are high, ensuring a relatively low threat of new entrants. These barriers include high startup costs, such as establishing infrastructure, hiring qualified staff, and acquiring necessary resources. Additionally, government regulations regarding class sizes (e.g., minimum of 20 students per class) can further limit the entry of new schools, contributing to a lower likelihood of new competitors emerging [4].

- Power of suppliers

The school has access to many suppliers of educational materials and services. This high availability of suppliers reduces the bargaining power of individual suppliers and gives the school more leverage to negotiate favorable terms and prices. The school can source materials and services from various suppliers, ensuring competitive pricing and maintaining quality standards. So, the power of suppliers considered as low.

- Power of customers

The power of customers is high due to the presence of many competitors and a wide range of choices available to parents. This leads to low switching costs, as parents have the flexibility to choose alternative schools if they are dissatisfied. As a result, Inclusion Primary School needs to prioritize the delivery of high-quality education, tailored support for students with diverse needs, and comprehensive services to attract and retain students and their families.

- Threat of substitute products

The threat of substitute products, such as non-formal education options, is relatively low. Non-formal education can serve as a complementary option to formal education but cannot fully replace the comprehensive curriculum and structured learning environment provided by primary schools. Inclusion Primary School can focus on highlighting the unique benefits of formal education and emphasizing the inclusive and specialized services it offers, mitigating the potential impact of substitute products.

3) PESTLE

- Political

The amount of government funding that Alfa Centauri Primary School receives is critical in determining the school's financial stability and resources. It is critical to evaluate the amount of funding received as well as any potential future changes or fluctuations. The zoning policies in the area where the school is located can impact the school's catchment area and student enrollment. If public schools based on zoning are seen as having poor quality and cannot answer the needs of parents, then private schools will be the choice. So political aspect is an opportunity for Alfa Centauri Primary School.

- Economic

The economic growth rate of the city of Bandung is 5.41% in 2022, which in 2020 will decrease by 2.28% and in 2021 it will grow only by 3.76% [16]. Bandung's economic growth rate may have an indirect impact on the school's finances. Changes in the rate of economic growth may affect parents' financial capabilities and their ability to afford private education, which may impact enrollment numbers. So economical aspect is an opportunity for Alfa Centauri Primary School.

- Social

The current societal trend of parents is enrolling their children in private schools rather than public schools. This aspect is important for understanding the competitive landscape and potential student enrollment. Factors such as perceived quality, reputation, and individual preferences can also influence enrollment decisions. So social aspect is an opportunity for Alfa Centauri Primary School.

- Technology

The availability and quality of e-learning supporting facilities, such as computers, internet connectivity, and digital resources, are essential for effective online learning. School's infrastructure and resources in this regard are crucial in adapting to the growing demand for e-learning. So technological aspect is an opportunity for Alfa Centauri Primary School.

- Legal

There is a government policy on the minimum number of students per class that helps determine class sizes and student-teacher ratios (20-28 students per class) [4]. This policy has implications for the quality of education provided and the level of individual attention students can receive. Space allocation per student in the classrooms is also a legal and crucial aspect for ensuring a comfortable and conducive learning environment (2m² per student) [17]. Sufficient space is needed for students to move around, access learning materials, and engage in collaborative activities. Bandung City Government's inclusiveness policies (since 2018) for all elementary schools [18]. In fact, not all schools can implement an inclusion system so that only a few schools are "ready" to accept students from all walks of life. Hence, this becomes an important thing for Alfa Centauri Primary School for promoting diversity, inclusion, and equal opportunities for all students. Understanding the school's commitment to inclusivity is vital for evaluating its overall environment and educational approach. So legal aspect is an opportunity for Alfa Centauri Primary School.

- Environment

The school's location in a congested area can present challenges related to traffic congestion and limited parking space. These factors are important things to consider for the smooth functioning of the school's operations, including student drop-off and pick-up procedures. So environmental aspect is a threat for Alfa Centauri Primary School.

4) *Customer Analysis*

Customer analysis is carried out based on questionnaires that have been distributed to potential customers, namely parents who have children with a maximum age of 12 years. Realization of the number of respondents in this study amounted to 215 respondents. The

Table 6 shows the demographic analysis of the respondents who filled out the research questionnaire.

Table 6. Respondents demography

Demography Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	39	18.1%
Female	176	81.9%
Age		
<30	101	47%
31-40	74	34.4%
41-50	38	17.7%
51-60	2	0.9%
Education		
Junior High School	5	2.3%
Senior High School	57	26.5%
Associate Degree 1	4	1.9%
Associate Degree 2	11	5.1%
Bachelor's Degree	120	55.8%
Master's Degree	12	5.6%
Doctoral Degree	1	.5%
Other	5	2.3%
Occupation		
Freelancer	34	15.8%
Teacher	7	3.3%

Housewife	53	24.7%
College Student	12	5.6%
Government Employee	19	8.8%
Private Employee	59	27.4%
Entrepreneur	22	10.2%
Other	9	4.2%
Income (in Rp)		
<10.000.000	152	70.7%
10.000.001-20.000.000	36	16.7%
20.000.001-30.000.000	12	5.6%
30.000.001-40.000.000	2	0.9%
40.000.001-50.000.000	5	2.3%
50.000.001-60.000.000	3	1.4%
>70.000.000	5	2.3%

Table 7 shows the calculation of the validity and reliability of the data obtained. SP1 indicator variable is excluded from the calculation because it causes the SP composite variable to be unreliable. Based on this analysis, all indicator variables and composite variables can be said to be valid and reliable so that the next step can be carried out, namely regression analysis in testing the research hypothesis.

Table 7. Validity and reliability analysis

Indicator Variable	Sig. (2-tailed)	Pearson Correlation	Cronbach Alpha
Cut-Off Value	< .005	≥.138	≥ .6
CS – School Curriculum and Syllabus			.643
CS1	≤.001	.789	
CS2	≤.001	.745	
CS3	≤.001	.767	
EF – School Environment and Facilities			.735
EF1	≤.001	.794	
EF2	≤.001	.704	
EF3	≤.001	.715	
EF4	≤.001	.670	
EF5	≤.001	.673	
SP – School Performance			.798
SP2	≤.001	.677	
SP3	≤.001	.757	
L – School Location			.642
L1	≤.001	.629	
L2	≤.001	.836	
L3	≤.001	.819	
TQ – Teachers’ Quality			.744
TQ1	≤.001	.798	
TQ2	≤.001	.812	
TQ3	≤.001	.836	
I – Parent’s Intention to Enroll Their Children			.968
I1	≤.001	.941	
I2	≤.001	.953	

I3	<.001	.939
I4	<.001	.940
I5	<.001	.939

Furthermore, the **Table 8** shows the calculation of the descriptive analysis of the data obtained, in which the descriptive analysis consists of the mean, median, mode, and standard deviation of each indicator variable and composite variable which aims to obtain the frequency distribution of the data.

Table 8. Descriptive analysis

Indicator Variable	Mean	Median	Mode	Standard Deviation
CS – School Curriculum and Syllabus	4.76	5	5	.414
CS1	4.83	5	5	.483
CS2	4.76	5	5	.559
CS3	4.69	5	5	.579
EF – School Environment and Facilities	4.28	4.40	5	.564
EF1	4.07	4	4	.826
EF2	4.48	5	5	.663
EF3	4.55	5	5	.667
EF4	4.30	4	5	.794
EF5	4.01	4	5	1.059
SP – School Performance	4.48	4.67	5	.492
SP1	3.89	4	4	.944
SP2	4.80	5	5	.498
SP3	4.75	5	5	.531
L – School Location	4.19	4.33	5	.633
L1	4.62	5	5	.575
L2	4.14	4	5	.880
L3	3.80	4	4	.981
TQ – Teachers’ Quality	4.60	5	5	.517
TQ1	4.66	5	5	.597
TQ2	4.66	5	5	.582
TQ3	4.50	5	5	.723
I – Parent’s Intention to Enroll Their Children	3.66	3.67	3	1.013
I1	3.69	4	3	1.068
I2	3.64	4	3	1.072
I3	3.66	4	3	1.028
I4	3.46	3	3	1.084
I5	3.45	3	3	1.105

This study uses Principal Component Analysis (PCA), which is one of the tools in exploratory factor analysis to group variables based on the same basic dimensions (factors) [19]. This study uses PCA with varimax rotation which is applied to all independent variables. So that we get a new grouping of indicator variables along with the naming of the new composite variable (independent variable) shown in the **Table 9**.

Table 9. List of variables after PCA

New Independent Variable	Indicator Variable Before PCA	Indicator Variable After PCA
School Environment (37.52%)	EF1	SE1
	EF2	SE2
	EF3	SE3
	EF4	SE4
	SP2	SE5
	SP3	SE6
Teacher's Quality (10.87%)	TQ1	TQ1
	TQ2	TQ2
	TQ3	TQ3
Ethical and Ecological Orientation (7.82%)	CS1	EE1
	CS2	EE2
	L1	EE3
School Accessibility (7.28%)	L2	SA1
	L3	SA2
	EF5	SA3

SP1 and CS3 indicator variables are not included in the formulation of the new variable because they have low loading factors. In addition, four new variables are formed as new independent variables because there are four components that have eigenvalues above number 1, and these four new variables explain 63.50% of the variance. The first factor accounts for 37.52% of the variance and has similarity in environmental aspects, so the name for the first variable is called school environment. The second factor accounts for 10.87% of the variance and there is no change in the indicator variables, namely questions about teacher's quality. The third factor accounts for 7.82% of the variance which is a pairing of curriculum-syllabus and location (convenience environment) aspects, so that the naming of the third variable is ethical and ecological orientation. The last factor accounts for 7.28% of the variance which has similarity in terms of accessibility for students, so the name for the last variable is school accessibility. Based on the change in the arrangement of the independent variables, a new research framework was formulated on the **Figure 4**:

Figure 4. Research framework after PCA

After PCA is done, hypothesis adjustments are also made according to the new variables (see **Table 10**):

Table 10 Research hypothesis after PCA

Hypotheses	Descriptions
H ₁	School environment has a positive effect on parents' intention to enroll their child(ren) to public inclusive school
H ₂	Teacher's quality has a positive effect on parents' intention to enroll their child(ren) to public inclusive school
H ₃	Ethical & ecological orientation has a positive effect on parent's intention to enroll their child(ren) to public inclusive school
H ₄	School accessibility has a positive effect on parents' intention to enroll their child(ren) to public inclusive school

Furthermore, regression analysis was performed to test the research hypothesis. The results of the regression calculations show that there are two hypotheses that are accepted because they have a significance value of <.05, namely hypothesis 1 and hypothesis 4 (see

Table 11).

Table 11. Regression results

	t value	Sig.
School environment	2.555	0.11
Teacher's quality	.524	.601
Ethical & ecological orientation	.953	.342
School accessibility	3.477	<.001

For hypothesis 1, the school environment is proven to be a consideration for parents' intention to enroll their child(ren) to public inclusive school. This is in line with the findings of [6], [8] that the school environment is one of the considerations for parents in sending their children to school. For hypothesis 4, school accessibility is proven to be a consideration for parents' intention to enroll their child(ren) to public inclusive school. The strategic and close location of the school, as well as the smaller class sizes describe the variables of school accessibility. This is in line with the research of [6], [8] which states that smaller class sizes are a consideration for parents in choosing a school for their child. Another study [20] stated that obstacles to students' access to school had a negative effect on their educational performance. School accessibility has a positive correlation with school attendance rates, which is also a factor in the effectiveness of teaching and learning activities [21].

In addition to testing the hypothesis, the researcher also conducted a regression test using a dummy variable from the demographics of the respondents to gain insights on the comparison of deviation between one nominal data group and the reference category in relation to the dependent variable [19]. The regression results are used if the significance value is <.05. The reference category used for each demographic is the demographic group with the largest number (assuming it represents the demographic population), including female (gender), <30 y.o. (age), bachelor's degree (education), housewife (occupation), and <10,000,000 (income). The insights obtained are that parents who work as government employees compared to housewives are more likely to enroll their child(ren) in public inclusive schools. The R square of the regression results in this research model is .214.

BUSINESS SOLUTIONS

Through the SWOT analysis, each obtained nine strengths, three weaknesses, thirteen opportunities, and seven threats. From all the SWOT lists obtained, strategies are formulated using the TOWS matrix and priority elaboration using QSPM.

Table 12. TOWS matrix

	<p>Strengths</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Proper physical building and infrastructure (VRIO) 2. Advanced technological resources for learning activities (VRIO) 3. Special and adjusted inclusive curriculum (VRIO) 4. Learning Support Unit (LSU) that supports inclusive learning activities (VRIO) 5. Good reputation and brand image especially in the educational industry (VRIO) 6. Strategic partnership that give more value to customers (VRIO) 7. “A” accredited school (STP) 8. Good and relevant educational value (Marketing Mix) 9. Omni-channel promotional tools (Marketing Mix) 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The building area is limited (not large enough) in accommodating students (VRIO, Marketing Mix) 2. Low-quality photo or video production on social media promotion (Marketing Mix) 3. Social media content type tends to provide information, less on telling stories and interactive content (Marketing Mix)
<p>Opportunities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Complete and clear information through social media compared to other competitors (Competitor Analysis) 2. Active on social media activity compared to other competitors (Competitor Analysis) 3. Compared to well-known competitors (private schools), Alfa Centauri can provide inclusive education (Competitor Analysis) 4. More content type on Instagram (Competitor Analysis) 5. Bad impact on zoning policy can lead parents to enrol their child(ren) to inclusive school (PESTLE) 6. Growth in economic aspects on Bandung society (PESTLE) 7. Societal trend of parents is enrolling their children in private schools rather than public schools (PESTLE) 8. Few school in Bandung City can implement inclusive education system (PESTLE) 	<p>Strengths-Opportunities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Brand image enhancement through social media marketing; capitalizing the good reputation, inclusivity, strategic partnership, and customer value (S3,S4,S5,S7,O1,O2,O3) 2. Leverage strategic partnerships in educational field to provide additional value to customers and differentiate from competitors (S6,O7,O8,O10) 3. Provision of shuttle services coordinated by the school to provide easy access to schools (S1,O12) 4. Utilization and optimization of personalization in teaching and learning services, including delivery of learning outcome data, personalized treatment, and appreciation of learning outcomes (S2,S3,S4,S6,O5,O7,O8,O9) 	<p>Weaknesses- Opportunities</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prioritizing and communicating that learning environment is comfortable and "homey" for all students (W1,W3,O1,O2,O11,O12) 2. Improve social media activity with proper production, by incorporating storytelling and interactive content, and leveraging the opportunity to provide diverse content types on social media (W2,W3,O1,O2,O4)

<p>9. High barrier to entry is an opportunity to claim the market share (Porter's Five Forces)</p> <p>10. Non-formal education cannot replace/substitute formal education (Porter's Five Forces)</p> <p>11. School environment is a consideration for parents to enroll their child(ren) to inclusive school (Customer Analysis)</p> <p>12. School accessibility is a consideration for parents to enroll their child(ren) to inclusive school (Customer Analysis)</p> <p>13. Government employee compared to housewife more likely enroll their child(ren) to inclusive school (Customer Analysis)</p>		
<p>Threats</p> <p>1. Several competitors have good content productions for social media (Competitor Analysis)</p> <p>2. Competitor has broader <i>yayanan</i> coverage (Competitor Analysis)</p> <p>3. Some competitors located in strategic location (Competitor Analysis)</p> <p>4. There is a minimum number of students regulation in one class, that restrict/limit the students distribution (PESTLE)</p> <p>5. School's location in a congested area (PESTLE)</p> <p>6. High competition in the elementary school industry (Porter's Five Forces)</p> <p>7. High power of customers (Porter's Five Forces)</p>	<p>Strengths-Threats</p> <p>1. Focus on providing excellent customer services, improve parental engagement, and enhancing inclusivity execution (S2,S3,S4,S8,T6,T7)</p> <p>2. Building a mutually supportive ecosystem between schools-parents-alumni-private parties, related to improving the quality of learning, unique experiences, and diversity of services (S6,T2,T6)</p>	<p>Weaknesses-Threats</p> <p>1. Improvement on social media marketing and social media maintenance to make it more engaging and interactive to the audiences, also point out the differentiation compared with competitors (W2,W3,T1,T6)</p> <p>2. Utilization of outdoor activities and outings for room exploration or learning facilities other than class (W1,T4)</p>

In carrying out QSPM calculations, several strategies are selected in advance to be sorted according to company priorities. The ten strategies above can be simplified by merging several similar strategies. Strategy 1-6-9 which both have the theme of enhancement in social media activity can be used as one strategy, as well as strategy 2-7-8 which has similarities in terms of strategic partnership and the creation of an ecosystem that involves various parties. After the calculation process is carried out based on the weighting and ranking of each factor that influences the formulated strategy, the following is the sequence of strategies based on QSPM calculations in **Table 13**:

Table 13. QSPM Calculation

Strategy	QSPM Score
Brand image enhancement through social media marketing and social media maintenance with proper production; capitalizing the good reputation, inclusivity, strategic partnership, customer value, and other diverse content to make it more engaging and interactive to the audiences.	6.66
Leverage strategic partnerships and building a mutually supportive ecosystem in educational field to provide additional value to customers, differentiate from competitors, improve quality of learning, and make unique experiences.	7.37
Provision of shuttle services coordinated by the school to provide easy access to schools	4.72
Utilization and optimization of personalization in teaching and learning services, including delivery of learning outcome data, personalized treatment, and appreciation of learning outcomes	7.93
Prioritizing and communicating that the learning environment is comfortable and "homey" for all students	7.38
Utilization of outdoor activities and outings for room exploration or learning facilities other than class	7.91

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

Specifically, based on customer analysis conducted using a survey questionnaires method, there are two hypotheses which are the findings of factors influencing enrollment intention of Alfa Centauri Primary School, including school environment and school accessibility. Aspects of the school environment that can be considered include physical school building, school facilities, quality of school management, social perspectives, healthy teaching and learning environment, and school environment cleanliness. As for the aspect of school accessibility, the strategic and close location of the school, as well as the smaller class sizes describe the variables of school accessibility. In addition, additional insight is obtained that parents with civil servant jobs compared to housewives are more likely to enroll their child(ren) in public inclusive schools. The factors above can be used by Alfa Centauri Primary School as a basis for making improvements to get optimal performance in getting customers. Based on a series of internal-external analysis stages, SWOT, TOWS matrix, and QSPM, several strategies have been formulated that are expected to increase the number of registrants for Alfa Centauri Primary School **Table 13**.

B. Recommendation

The framework used in this study adopts the previous research framework from [6], which formed five hypotheses and then reduced to four hypotheses through PCA (see **Table 9**). This research produces new findings that are different from previous research, namely that there are two hypotheses that are accepted and two hypotheses that are rejected. The finding that the school environment is a factor that parents consider in sending their children to inclusive private primary schools is in line with the findings of [6], [8] that the school environment is one of the considerations for parents in sending their children to private schools (in general). The PCA technique that was applied to the research and also as an exploratory factor analysis resulted in two other equivalent variables that could be used as the basis for further research, namely ethical & ecological orientation and school accessibility variables. Variable school accessibility has proven to be a consideration for parents in sending their children to private inclusive elementary school, this is in line with [20] that obstacles to students' access to school had a negative effect on their educational performance. [21] also stated that school accessibility has a positive correlation with school attendance rates, which is also a factor in the effectiveness of teaching and learning activities. Another finding in this study is that teacher's quality is not a consideration for parents in sending their children to private inclusive elementary school, which is a different finding from [6]. The R square result from the survey that has been conducted is only .214, of which there are still approximately .786 which represents the many variables that influence parent's intention to enroll their child(ren). So further research is needed to explore and find these other variables.

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